

LONG-TERM OBSERVATION OF A FAMILY TUBERCULOSIS FOCUS

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ANNOTATSIIYA: Sil infeksiyasi o'chog'i deb mikobakteriyalar manbai bo'lgan bemor yashaydigan joy bo'lib, u yerda yashovchi yoki doimiy aloqada bo'lgan shaxslar tuberkulyoz infeksiyasini yuqtirish xavfi ostida bo'ladilar. SIO`dagi kasallanish ko'plab omillar bilan belgilanadi, jumladan kasallik manbasining klinik shakli, bakteriya ajratish darajasi, dori vositalariga chidamlilik spektri, shuningdek, ijtimoiy-gigiyenik sharoitlar va kontakt shaxslarning individual xavf omillari bilan bog'liq. Mazkur maqolada oilaviy sil infeksiyasi o'chog'ida tuberkulyozning rivojlanish xususiyatlari va uzoq muddatli kuzatuv natijalari tahlil qilindi. Kuzatuv 4 kishilik oilada olib borilgan bo'lib, unda bir vaqtning o'zida ikki o'g'ilda o'pka tuberkulyozi aniqlangan. Ulardan birida OIV-infeksiya fonida ekssudativ plevrit rivojlangan bo'lsa, ikkinchisida disseminatsiya tuberkulyoz va massiv bakteriya ajratish kuzatilgan. O'choqda sanitariya-epidemiologik tadbirlar o'tkazilgan, kontakt shaxslarga kimyoprofilaktika tayinlangan va dispanser kuzatuv amalga oshirilgan. Shunga qaramay, 6 yil SIO`b ota-onada ham tuberkulyoz aniqlangan, bu esa oilaviy SIO`da uzoq muddatli epidemiologik xavf saqlanib qolishini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari sil infeksiyasi o'choqlarida kontakt shaxslarni kuzatish muddatlarini individual ravishda uzaytirish zarurligini hamda bir nechta oila a'zolari kasallangan o'choqlarni alohida epidemiologik guruh sifatida ko'rib chiqish maqsadga muvofiqligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sil o'chog'i, oilaviy kontaktlar, o'pka tuberkulyozi, OIV-infeksiya, epidemiologik xavf, kimyoprofilaktika, dispanser kuzatuv.

АННОТАЦИЯ: Очаг туберкулёзной инфекции — это место проживания пациента, являющегося источником микобактерий, где лица, проживающие или находящиеся в постоянном контакте, подвергаются риску заражения туберкулёзной инфекцией. Заболеваемость в очаге определяется множеством факторов, включая клиническую форму болезни источника, степень выделения бактерий, спектр устойчивости к лекарственным средствам, а также социально-гигиенические условия и индивидуальные факторы риска контактных лиц. В данной статье проанализированы особенности развития туберкулёза и результаты долгосрочного наблюдения в семейном очаге инфекции. Наблюдение проводилось в семье из четырёх человек, в которой одновременно у двух сыновей выявлен туберкулёз лёгких. У одного из них развился экссудативный плеврит на фоне ВИЧ-инфекции, у другого — диссеминированный туберкулёз с массивным выделением бактерий. В очаге были проведены санитарно-эпидемиологические мероприятия, контактными лицам назначена химиопрофилактика, осуществлено диспансерное наблюдение. Тем не менее, через шесть лет у родителей также выявлен туберкулёз, что свидетельствует о сохранении долгосрочного эпидемиологического риска в семейном очаге. Результаты исследования показывают необходимость индивидуального продления сроков наблюдения за контактными лицами и целесообразность рассмотрения очагов, в которых заболели несколько членов семьи, как отдельной эпидемиологической группы.

Ключевые слова: очаг туберкулёза, семейные контакты, туберкулёз лёгких, ВИЧ-инфекция, эпидемиологический риск, химиопрофилактика, диспансерное наблюдение.

ABSTRACT: A tuberculosis infection focus is the place of residence of a patient who is the source of mycobacteria, where individuals living or in constant contact are at risk of contracting tuberculosis. Morbidity within the focus is determined by multiple factors, including the clinical form of the source case, the degree of bacterial excretion, the spectrum of drug resistance, as well as socio-hygienic conditions and individual risk factors of contacts. This article analyzes the features of

tuberculosis development and the results of long-term observation in a family infection focus. The observation was conducted in a family of four, in which two sons were simultaneously diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis. One developed exudative pleuritis against the background of HIV infection, while the other had disseminated tuberculosis with massive bacterial excretion. Sanitary and epidemiological measures were carried out in the focus, chemoprophylaxis was prescribed to contacts, and dispensary follow-up was implemented. Nevertheless, six years later, tuberculosis was also detected in the parents, indicating the persistence of long-term epidemiological risk in the family focus. The study results highlight the need for individualized extension of follow-up periods for contacts and the advisability of considering foci where several family members fall ill as a separate epidemiological group.

Keywords: tuberculosis focus, family contacts, pulmonary tuberculosis, HIV infection, epidemiological risk, chemoprophylaxis, dispensary follow-up.

A tuberculosis infection focus (TBF) is a place of permanent residence of a source of mycobacteria (MBT), from which people living around it are at risk of infection. The level of epidemic risk varies, the highest risk is observed in the first group of foci, that is, in places where patients with active pulmonary tuberculosis and excreting a large number of bacteria live. Secondary infection of contact persons in TBF is not stable, but according to the literature, this indicator is dozens of times higher than the incidence rate in the general population. In family TBF, tuberculosis cases are detected at a rate of 1.5%–3.4%, the incidence reaches its peak in the first year of established contact. Active pulmonary tuberculosis is detected in 3.5%–5.5%. The probability of latent tuberculosis infection (LTI) in household contacts increases with age, and its reactivation can occur after decades. The prevalence of LTI was 47% in children under 6 years of age, 53% in the age group 6–14 years, and 78% in the age group 15–45 years.

Incidence in SIO is a multifactorial indicator, which is determined by the characteristics of the course of the source tuberculosis (clinical form, duration, amount of bacterial isolation, drug resistance spectrum of MBT), socio-hygienic conditions in the focus (living space, ventilation, sunlight, humidity level, anti-epidemic measures) and risk factors of contact persons.

Some researchers argue that the incidence of SIO is higher in patients with drug-sensitive tuberculosis, while others note the opposite. The incidence of SIO is heterogeneous and is often characterized by late detection and the development of severe destructive processes, existing or acquired resistance of MBT to drugs, and high epidemic risk.

Our goal is to analyze observations of two periods of tuberculosis disease in a family home. Social characteristics of the tuberculosis infection center. A family of 4 people (father, mother and two adult sons) lived in the home. Social and household conditions were satisfactory, each family member had a separate room. The house was regularly cleaned and the rooms were ventilated. At the same time, the family was socially disadvantaged, had low material resources, and insufficient medical and sanitary literacy. Father and mother are pensioners. The eldest son is 32 years old, neurologically disabled (toxic encephalopathy), professional activity is unknown, HIV-positive. The younger son is 28 years old, worked as an electric welder, used narcotic drugs (opiates) for 10 years, was infected with viral hepatitis C, HIV-negative.

Epidemiological description of SIO. Pulmonary pathology was detected when the eldest son applied to the general medical network (GMT) with complaints of shortness of breath during physical exertion and general weakness. After examination by a phthisiatrician, he was diagnosed with left-sided exudative pleurisy, MBT (–) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Chest radiographs of the eldest son:
a – at the time of the initial visit, b – at the time of the repeated visit

Treatment of the patient. The patient was admitted to a tuberculosis inpatient hospital for treatment. Here, antibodies to HIV were detected for the first time. Immune status – 613 cells/ μ l. A diagnostic thoracotomy with biopsy of the left pleura was performed, as a result of which pleural tuberculosis was histologically confirmed. Isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and ethambutol were used as the treatment plan. The treatment gave a positive result, but the patient stopped treatment after 3 months due to the fact that he was leaving for another country.

After the diagnosis of tuberculosis in the eldest son, the results of the SIO examination: mother and father – healthy; lung pathology was detected in the younger son.

Younger son. Diagnosis: infiltrative tuberculosis in the S3 segment of the left lung, infiltrative tuberculosis in the lower lobe of the right lung, MBT (+). The diagnosis was confirmed bacteriologically (bacterioscopy and culture), MBT was sensitive to isoniazid and rifampicin. Antibodies to viral hepatitis C (anti-HCV) were detected, HIV status was negative. After a narcological examination, a diagnosis of “opiate dependence syndrome” was made.

The patient was hospitalized for tuberculosis, and a treatment plan based on isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and ethambutol was used. The treatment gave good results, and stable abstinence was achieved up to 60 doses. However, after 3 months of treatment, the patient’s condition deteriorated sharply due to drug use. The patient died in the hospital against the background of pulmonary-cardiac failure and increased intoxication.

Pathoanatomical diagnosis: disseminated tuberculosis and right-sided serous-fibrinous pleurisy.

Return of the eldest son. Returning to his place of residence, the eldest son immediately turned to a phthisiatrician. Complaints: severe shortness of breath and worsening intoxication syndrome. According to the results of the examination: HIV infection, secondary diseases stage 4B, progression phase without antiretroviral therapy (ART); right-sided exudative pleurisy, MBT (–) (Fig. 1, b). Immune status - 516 cells/ μ l.

Treatment plan: isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and ethambutol. A total of 120 doses were taken in the intensive phase, and 120 doses in the supportive phase. As a result, the fluid in the pleural cavity was absorbed. The patient was transferred to group 3 dispensary observation. After the intensive phase of tuberculosis chemotherapy was completed, he began taking ART.

Sanitary and anti-epidemic measures in the SIO. Contact persons were isolated by hospitalization in an anti-tuberculosis hospital. The father and mother were prescribed chemoprophylaxis based on isoniazid and rifampicin for 3 months. Regular sanitary and educational work was carried out in the center, and the regimen measures were fully implemented. Contact persons were under control during the entire period of dispensary observation and underwent an X-ray examination every 6 months. After 3 years, they were discharged from dispensary observation.

Subsequent events (after 6 years). The father, 67 years old, applied to the general treatment network (ODT) with complaints of febrile temperature, cough with sputum, and general weakness. After

discharge from dispensary observation, he did not undergo a fluorographic examination. The examination revealed pathology in the lungs (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Chest CT scan with pulmonary tuberculosis in the father

Consultation and diagnosis. The patient was consulted by a phthiatrician. The diagnosis was made: disseminated pulmonary tuberculosis, CV (+), MBT (+). MBT sensitivity to all major drugs was maintained. Treatment was initiated according to a standard regimen based on isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol.

In the intensive phase, stable abacillosis was achieved. However, during the planned radiological control in the continuation phase, disease progression was detected and bacterial isolation was restored. According to the results of the drug susceptibility test (DST), MBT resistance to rifampicin and isoniazid was detected. As a result, multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) was recorded. Final diagnosis: disseminated pulmonary tuberculosis, MBT (+), MDR (HR). Treatment was continued according to the following regimen: bedaquiline, linezolid, levofloxacin, clofazimine, and cycloserine.

Mother's condition. Mother, 62 years old. During the examination conducted as a contact person due to the diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis in her husband, pathology was detected in the lungs at

the polyclinic (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Chest X-ray when TB was detected in the mother

Results of radiological examination. Radiological examination revealed a tumor-like formation with clear boundaries in the right lung, with dense inclusions inside. ATP test - negative, MBT was not detected in sputum. As a result of consultation in the oncological dispensary, no evidence confirming the oncological process was found. Taking into account the epidemiological history and characteristic radiological signs, the following diagnosis was made: pulmonary tuberculoma, MBT (-), MDR (HR) (based on the results of the DST of the contact person). Treatment was carried out according to the following scheme: bedaquiline, linezolid, levofloxacin, clofazimine and cycloserine. The patient and his wife successfully completed the course of anti-tuberculosis treatment. Examination of the son did not reveal evidence confirming the recurrence of tuberculosis.

Note. Individuals living in a family tuberculosis infection center (FCU) are a group at high risk of developing tuberculosis. This is observed regardless of the clinical form, duration and intensity of

contact with the source [1, 4, 7]. One of the main areas of activity of anti-tuberculosis clinics in the foci is the prevention of the disease and its timely detection [1, 3, 5].

In this family FCU, it was difficult to identify the primary source of tuberculosis, since the pathology in the lungs was detected almost simultaneously in two boys, and both of them had significant risk factors. One of them (an injection drug user) was diagnosed with disseminated pulmonary tuberculosis and pleurisy, with massive bacterial excretion. In the second, exudative pleurisy was observed against the background of HIV infection, in which bacterial excretion was not detected. In the presented observation, despite the satisfactory socio-economic conditions in the center and the full implementation of anti-epidemic measures (prophylactic treatment of healthy contact persons - father and mother, and inpatient treatment of sick sons), after 6 years, tuberculosis was recorded in the contact persons in the SIO - father and mother. By that time, they had been removed from dispensary observation and had stopped undergoing regular preventive examinations. As a result, the father's disease was detected in the destruction stage when he applied to the medical institution with complaints, and in the mother's during the contact examination, it was detected in the stage of tuberculoma formation.

Although the periods of observation of SIO are regulated, in some cases it may be appropriate to extend them. This allows for additional monitoring and preventive measures. It is advisable to separate SIOs with several family members as a separate group, while it is necessary to develop individual observation plans for them, taking into account the possibility of a genetic predisposition to tuberculosis.

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